

STRENGTH PREDICTION OF EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITE

G. A. Forental*, S. B. Sapozhnikov

Physics Dept., South Ural State University, Chelyabinsk, Russia

*G. A. Forental (forental@newmail.ru)

Keywords: *epoxy resin, nanoparticles, strength, analytical model*

1 Introduction

Addition of micro- and nanoparticles to polymer material allows getting composite with improved characteristics as strength, durability, thermal conductivity, moisture absorption and etc. Nanometer-scale filler allows increasing the strength of polymer materials by 20–25% [1–4]. However, the strength of composite begins decreasing on reaching of certain volume fraction of particles. The model which can describe the non-monotone dependence of strength of epoxy nanocomposite on volume fraction of filler is suggested in present work.

Effects of strength increase, increase of modulus of elasticity and other properties are bound up with agglomerates of nanoparticles and the shape of these agglomerates. As shown in the work [4, 5], the shape of particle agglomerates dictated the shape of a majority of crosslinked epoxy domains.

There was introduced an interface layer around particles, and assumed that thickness of this layer does not depend on the size of particles in works [6, 7]. The presence of this layer explains breaking mixture laws of density of polymers in presence of fillers.

2 Electron microscopy of nanocomposite

To analyze the structure of nanocomposite and the distribution of particles into polymer the electron microscope (JEOL GEM-2100) of nanocomposite was used.

The samples were made of epoxy resin, room hardening agent – polyethylene polyamine and filler – nanoparticles of silicon oxide (average diameter 9 nm) with volume fraction $V=1\%$.

Epoxy resin and nanoparticles were mixed using planetary-type mill AGO-2U under temperature 25°C during 20 minutes, and then prepared mixture was vacuumized. The temperature of mixing is determined the operating conditions of planetary-

type mill (cooling of vessels with compound by cold water) and is not changed during the process of mixing.

Mixture time was chosen after series of experiments which was taken in two stages. The first stage is careful observation of mixture (homogeneity without visible agglomerates). The second stage is devoted to control of compound viscosity. Viscosity was measured with rotational viscometer Brookfield R/S *plus* during the process of mixing. Addition of fine filler to resin leads to increasing the viscosity of compound. This process is asymptotical in time scale. The mixing time was stated when the viscosity of the mixture had become the maximum value.

After mixing of epoxy resin with nanoparticles the hardening agent was added to this compound 2 minutes before the end of mixing. Epoxy resin creates the layer around every particle and has sufficiently high viscosity which hinders from the sedimentation of particles. Then it is possible to avoid the return agglomeration of nanoparticles adding the hardening agent.

The samples were cured in open forms under room temperature during 12 hours. Then thin films were cut out of prepared samples using microtome. The thickness of films was about 200 nm.

The results of use of transmission electron microscopy are presented in the figure 1a. It is easy to see the nanoparticles of silicon oxide create the elongate structures of different sizes (from 40 till 150 nm) – the long chains of nanoparticles. We can say here that creation of these long structures inside nanocomposite is the main goal of good mixing.

As is shown in work [8], the filling of polymer with nanoparticles increases the nanocomposite strength. At that the transmission electron microscopy results show that the dispersed phases in the nanocomposites are much larger than the size of the primary nanoparticles of silicon oxide. And the agglomerates of nanoparticles have the elongate form. In the figure 1b the results are presented for polypropylene filled grafted nanoparticles of silicon

oxide (nanoparticles were coated with polystyrene, average size of nanoparticles – 7 nm).

3 Determination of the properties of interface layer

To determine the strength of nanocomposite here we use the idea of interface matrix layer around particle. The properties of interface layer are determined using two groups of experiments: measurement of density and modulus of elasticity of nanocomposite with different volume fraction of filler. In order to determine the properties of this specific layer the following assumptions were introduced: the particles of filler are equal and spherical, have known diameter and volume fraction, and are situated at the cube corners. The interface layer has constant thickness around every particle. The properties of particles, interface layer and matrix are constants (it is obvious the interface layer does not have abrupt change to matrix as layer and matrix have the same nature. However, the considerations of simplicity force us to use this model of the piecewise function of polymer properties).

The composite density is determined as the function of component properties, eq. (1):

$$\rho(\delta, V) = \rho_p \cdot V + \rho_l \cdot V_l + \rho_m \cdot (1 - V - V_l), \quad (1)$$

where δ – interface layer thickness; V – nanoparticle volume fraction; ρ_p – density of nanoparticles; ρ_l – layer density; $V_l = V \cdot \left[\left(1 + \delta \frac{2}{d} \right)^3 - 1 \right]$ – interface layer volume fraction; d – nanoparticle diameter, ρ_m – bulk matrix density.

Two parameters can change: density and thickness of interface layer. If we use the assumption of low density of layer ($\rho_l \approx 0$), then the thickness δ of layer will be about 3 nm. If $\rho_l = 0,55\rho_m$ the thickness δ is about 6 nm. So there is uncertainty which can be solved using additional information. It can be the elastic modulus of nanocomposite.

The interface layer is formed by radial oriented molecules of polymer which were created during thermally induced curing process near surface of particle and it gives high modulus of elasticity of this layer. In this case it is possible to couple formally this layer with filler because the modulus of elasticity of such layer is much higher than the matrix modulus. The effective volume fraction of such couple is higher than volume fraction of only nanoparticles. For known diameter of particles and thickness of interface layer the effective volume

fraction V_e and the filler volume fraction V are connected with the constant k :

$$V_e = k \cdot V. \quad (2)$$

In this case the modulus of elasticity of nanocomposite can be calculated using empirical law, eq. (3), which allows finding out the modulus of elasticity of composite with *rigid* macrofiller [9] taking into account effective volume fraction, eq. (2):

$$\frac{E}{E_m} = e^{3,0 \cdot V_e}, \quad (3)$$

where E – the modulus of elasticity of filled polymer; E_m – matrix modulus of elasticity.

In order to determine the density and thickness of interface layer, and constant k the experiments were conducted using samples made of room hardening epoxy resin filled with nanoparticles of silicon oxide (average diameter 70 nm), volume fractions $V=0..4\%$, hardening agent – polyethylene polyamine. Mixing and curing technology were the same one as discussed in the chapter 2.

The samples of epoxy nanocomposites with different volume fraction of filler had sizes $25 \times 5 \times 2$ mm and were tested by cyclical tension using dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA 242C, Netzsch). Frequency of cycling was 1 Hz, load amplitude – 1 N, average load – 0.8 N. Temperature was varied from 25 till 40°C.

Experimental and calculated values of relative modulus of elasticity are shown in the figure 2 (points – experiments, line – calculation by eq. (3) for $k=2.89$).

The nanocomposite density was measured using the method of submergence into distilled water.

Experimental results and theoretical function of density of epoxy nanocomposite versus volume fraction of nanoparticles are shown in the figure 3 (points – experimental mean values, line – calculation by using eq. (1) for $k=2.89$).

In this case the thickness of interface layer is $\delta=14.9$ nm and density – $\rho_l=0.98$ g/cm³. These values of characteristics of layer will be used below to define the strength of nanocomposite.

4 Determination of the strength of epoxy nanocomposite

4.1 Simulation of composite nanostructure

Nanoparticles inside resin agglomerates of arbitrary form (nanoclusters) after preliminary mixing by hand. The dimensions of these clusters are dozens or hundred times more the diameter of particles. During shear mixture the agglomerate of arbitrary form stretches into the line forming the “fiber” under the shear loading (figure 4). Thus, it is possible to consider that the “fiber” diameter is equal to the sum of nanoparticle diameter and thickness of interface layer which surrounds the particle [9]. The “fiber” length depends on the number of particles combining into “fiber”. So, epoxy composite filled with nanoparticles of silicon oxide could be considered as the sort of discontinuous fibers random reinforced composite. And the theory of discontinuous fibers can be used to determine the mechanical characteristics.

4.2 Prediction of nanocomposite strength

Using instead of fiber volume fraction V_f effective volume fraction of “filler and interface layer” V_e , it is possible to estimate the strength of nanocomposite with the help of well-known formulas for the strength of UD composite with discontinuous fibers [10]:

$$\sigma_{\parallel} = \left(\frac{\tau \cdot l}{d} \right) \cdot V_f + \sigma_m \cdot (1 - V_f), \text{ if } l < l_c; \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{\parallel} = \frac{2\tau \cdot l_c}{d} \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l} \right) \cdot V_f + \sigma_m \cdot (1 - V_f), \text{ } l \geq l_c,$$

where we use $\tau=30$ MPa – shear strength of matrix, l – fiber length, d – fiber diameter, V_f – fibers volume fraction, $\sigma_m=35$ MPa – matrix strength,

$l_c = \frac{\sigma_f \cdot d}{2\tau}$ – critical fiber length, σ_f – fiber strength

consists of nanoparticles edged interface layer.

Fiber strength is free parameter, its variation can change the results. The calculation was realized in case when all fibers have the length less than critical length. In this case the concrete value of fiber strength becomes inessential. So, we can use quite high value $\sigma_f=2000$ MPa or more.

As the strength of randomly oriented composite three times less than UD composite [11], solving (4) the composite strength is got as the function of aspect ratio l/d :

$$\sigma = \frac{\sigma_{\parallel} - \sigma_m}{3} + \sigma_m. \quad (5)$$

In order to determine the parameters of proposed model strength experiments were conducted. Epoxy nanocomposite of following composition was investigated: epoxy resin of room hardening filled with nanoparticles of silicon oxide (average diameter 110 nm), volume fractions $V=1$ и 5%, hardening agent – polyethylene polyamine. Three samples were made for each volume fraction. The mixture of silicon oxide nanoparticles and epoxy resin was made with planetary-type mill during 20 minutes with using of alumina grinding bodies.

The mean values of nanocomposite strength were: $\sigma=44$ MPa ($V=1\%$) and $\sigma=39$ MPa ($V=5\%$). These strengths are resulted for aspect ratio $l/d=31$ ($V=1\%$) and $l/d=2$ ($V=5\%$) taking into account eqs. (4) and (5).

Function of aspect ratio (“fiber” length l / diameter d) versus volume fraction of filler was supposed linear due to statistical base of breaking of agglomerates between grinding bodies. Taking into account finding value of aspect ratio l/d for volume fraction 1 and 5%, it turns out:

$$\frac{l}{d} = -7,25 \cdot V + 38,25. \quad (6)$$

4.3 Comparison of experimental and predicted values

In order to check supposed model the results of strength experiments of epoxy nanocomposite were used. Samples were made of epoxy resin filled with nanoparticles of silicon oxide (mean diameter 110 nm, volume fraction $V=1..5\%$) with polyethylene-polyamine as hardening agent. Three samples were tested for each volume fraction.

Solving (4), (5) and (6), the nanocomposite strengths were calculated for volume fractions of nanoparticles till 7%. The comparison of prediction and experiment shows that maximal error is about 6% for volume fraction $V=2\%$ (figure 5).

These results show that the nanocomposite strength decreases with the increasing of volume fraction and gets less than the pure epoxy resin strength. For example, for $V=7\%$ the nanocomposite strength $\sigma=34.7$ MPa, and the epoxy strength $\sigma=35$ MPa. At this case all particles are distributed uniformly and do not form fibers into polymer (aspect ratio $l/d=1$). So the filling of epoxy polymer with active silica nanoparticles is useless for volume fraction over 2%.

5 Conclusion

The model which can predict the strength of epoxy nanocomposite is proposed in this work on the base of the theory of discontinuous “fibers” which formed of nanoparticle agglomerates during mixing. This model can describe the non-monotone dependence of strength of epoxy nanocomposite vs. volume fraction of filler. The strength of epoxy nanocomposite is estimated to various volume fractions of nanoparticles. Discrepancies between experimental and predicted data do not exceed 6%. It is shown that the filling of epoxy resin with nanoparticles of silica over 2% vol. is useless.

a – size of nanoparticles SiO₂ 9 nm
(content of SiO₂= 1% vol.)

(some of chains of nanoparticles are marked)

b – size of nanoparticles SiO₂-g-PS 7 nm
(content of SiO₂= 6.38% vol.) [8]

Fig.1. Electron microscopy of filled nanocomposite.

Fig.2. Relative modulus of elasticity of nanocomposite vs. volume fraction of nanoparticles (line – prediction, points – experiments).

Fig.3. Density of nanocomposite vs. volume fraction of nanoparticles (points – experiment, line – prediction).

Fig.4. Formation of clusters of nanoparticles.

Fig.5. Strength of epoxy nanocomposite vs. filler volume fraction (line – prediction, points – experiment).

References

- [1] C.Wang and et. all “Polymers containing fullerene or carbon nanotube structures”. *Progress in Polymer Science*, 2004, Vol. 29, pp. 1079–1141.
- [2] M. F. Uddina, C.T. Sun “Strength of unidirectional glass/epoxy composite with silica nanoparticle-enhanced matrix”. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2008, Vol. 68, Issues 7-8, pp. 1637-1643.
- [3] O. Jacobs, B. Schädel and M. Cholewa “Verschleißminimierte Nano-Composites auf Epoxidharzbasis”. *ImpulsE*, 2004, Vol. 9, pp. 2-10.
- [4] J. Karger-Kocsis, S. Fakirov “*Nano- and Micromechanics of Polymer Blends and Composites*”. Hanser Publisher, 2009.
- [5] S.G. Advani “*Processing and properties of nanocomposites*”. World Scientific Publishing, 2007.
- [6] D.C. Edwards “Polymer-filler interactions in rubber reinforcement”. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1990, Vol. 25, No.12, p. 4175-4185.
- [7] J.E. Mark, B. Erman, F.R. Eirich “*Science and technology of rubber*”. 3rd edition, Elsevier Academic Press, 2005.
- [8] M. Z. Rong and et. all “Structure-property relationships of irradiation grafted nano-inorganic particle filled polypropylene composites”. *Polymer*, 2001, Vol. 42, pp. 167-183.
- [9] S.B. Sapozhnikov, G.A. Forental, N.V. Pleshko “Mixture law breaking for nanocomposites”. *Abstracts of XVI international conference “Mechanics of composite materials”*, Riga, CD-disk, 2010.
- [10] R. F. Gibson “*Principles of composite material mechanics*”. 2nd edition, CRC Press, 2007.
- [11] V.V. Vasilyev “*Mechanics of composite materials*”. Mashinostroenie, 1988 (in Russian).